

Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers as Predictor of Students' Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine which domains of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers predicts the students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China. 195 students were identified using the stratified sampling method. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design, employing two survey questionnaires focused on instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and Student's Interaction for data collection. Statistical tools used included mean, Pearson r, and regression analysis. Results indicated that the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of fairness and equity, student's involvement, feedback and communications, and technology in assessment was moderate which also means that it was sometimes observed. Moreover, on the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of interactive learning, cooperative learning, social development, and interpersonal competence garnered a mean score equivalent to moderate which also means that it was sometimes observed.. The findings also revealed a strong significant relationship between instructional appraisal approach of teachers and student's interaction ($p < .05$). Furthermore, fairness and equity, student's involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment significantly influenced student's interaction. Specifically, for every unit increase in these domains of instructional appraisal literacy, student's interaction increased by 1.908, holding other factors constant. Based on these findings, the study recommends that teachers should continue to refine their practices in providing equitable assessments and clear feedback. Enhancing student involvement in the assessment process and utilizing technology to support diverse learning needs are crucial areas for development.

Keyword: *Instructional Appraisal Literacy, Student's Interaction, Classroom Environment, Teachers, China.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

The lack of students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment can have significant implications for the teaching-learning processes. Without interaction, students may have limited exposure to diverse cultural perspectives. This can result in a lack of understanding and appreciation for the richness of various cultures, hindering the development of cultural competence. More so, the lack of students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom can impede the development of critical skills, hinder social and cultural understanding, and weaken the overall learning environment. Thus, encouraging and facilitating meaningful interactions among students from diverse backgrounds is essential for fostering a positive and enriching educational experience.

The report of Khalil et al. (2019) showed that limited interaction in diverse cultural classroom may hinder language development, especially for students who are learning a new language or have different language backgrounds. Lack of interaction deprives students of valuable opportunities to engage in cross-cultural

communication. This hinders the development of effective communication skills needed for collaboration in diverse workplaces and communities.

Also, Jennings et al. (2022) asserted that interactions among students often stimulate critical thinking as they discuss and analyze diverse perspectives. The absence of such interactions may limit students' exposure to alternative viewpoints, impeding the development of critical thinking skills. Likewise, the lack of diverse interactions may lead to an environment where students feel isolated or excluded, undermining the principles of inclusivity and diversity in education.

Taking things in the Philippine setting, Alvarez (2020) pointed out that the absence of students' interaction hinders the exchange of cultural perspectives and experiences. This limitation can result in a lack of cultural awareness and understanding among students, inhibiting the development of a culturally rich learning environment. Interactions among students provide opportunities for social learning. The lack of interaction diminishes the chances for collaborative problem-solving, peer teaching, and other

social learning experiences that contribute to a holistic educational experience. Also, Rotas (2020) found that the absence of students' interaction may result in impaired teamwork and collaboration, as students miss out on the opportunity to work with peers from diverse backgrounds.

In contrary, Khadka (2019) found that students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom promotes cultural awareness and sensitivity. Teachers at moderate levels need to be attuned to the cultural backgrounds of their students to create an inclusive and respectful learning environment. According to Zahin (2021), interacting with peers from diverse cultural backgrounds enriches students' learning experiences. Teachers can leverage this diversity to introduce varied perspectives, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of topics. Interacting with peers from diverse cultural backgrounds enriches students' learning experiences. Teachers can leverage this diversity to introduce varied perspectives, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of topics. Adding more, Wang (2019) noted that students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom prepares them for future endeavors. Moderate-level teachers play a key role in nurturing global competence by exposing students to different cultures, languages, and perspectives.

On the other hand, Rahimi et al. (2021) described teachers' instructional appraisal literacy as the teacher's understanding, competence, and proficiency in the evaluation and assessment of instructional practices. It involves the ability to critically assess the effectiveness of teaching methods, curriculum design, and overall instructional strategies. According to Popham (2019) that appraisal literacy enables teachers to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their instructional practices. This information allows them to tailor their teaching methods to better address the specific needs and learning styles of their students at moderate levels. Moreover, Hameed-Ur-Rehman and Baig (2022) noted that teachers with instructional appraisal literacy can effectively use data to inform their teaching. This includes analyzing assessment results, identifying patterns, and making data-driven decisions to adapt instruction based on student needs and progress.

On the other hand, previous studies showed that teachers' instructional appraisal literacy can significantly contribute to the improvement of students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment. For instance, Pennings et al. (2023), instructional appraisal literacy enables teachers to assess the effectiveness of their teaching strategies. By understanding which methods work best for diverse groups of students, teachers can tailor their approaches to enhance engagement and interaction among students from different cultural backgrounds. Also, Sembiring (2019) found that appraisal-literate teachers can identify the diverse learning styles present in the classroom. This understanding allows them to create instructional plans that cater to different preferences, promoting a more inclusive environment and facilitating increased student interaction.

While there is existing literature exploring the relationship between teachers' instructional practices and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environments, there remains a notable gap in understanding the specific influence of teachers' instructional appraisal literacy on facilitating and enhancing students' interaction within this context. Previous studies have often focused on general teaching practices, cultural competence, or instructional strategies, but there is a need for more targeted investigation into the impact of teachers' ability to appraise, assess, and adapt their instructional methods on fostering meaningful interaction among students from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Conducting a regression analysis is essential to address this research gap as it allows for a nuanced examination of the quantitative relationships between variables. Regression analysis can help identify the level to which teachers' instructional appraisal literacy predicts variations in students' interaction levels, considering other potentially influential factors. This statistical approach allows for a more precise exploration of the specific contribution of instructional appraisal literacy to the dynamics of student interaction in diverse cultural classrooms. The current study was conducted among students in Kang Chiao International School Xi'an Campus.

The primary objective of the study was to determine which domains of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers significantly influenced the students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environments in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

Specifically, the study will have the following objectives:

- What is the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of:
 - Fairness and equity;
 - Students' involvement;
 - Feedback and communication; and
 - Technology in assessment?
- What is the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of:
 - Interactive learning;
 - Cooperative learning;
 - Social development; and
 - Interpersonal competence?
- Is there a significant relationship between instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China?
- Do the domains of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers predicts the students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China?
- Ho1: There is no significant relationship between instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China.

- Ho2: The domains of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers predict the students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China.

II. METHOD

This section presented components of the methodology that was used in the study. These were research design, research respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedure, research ethics, and data analysis.

The researcher used a quantitative non-experimental design with a correlational approach to collect data. Quantitative research, as defined by Bhandari (2020), focuses on quantifying data collection and analysis through a deductive approach and is shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. Non-experimental research involves measuring variables as they naturally occur without manipulating them. The study employed descriptive-correlational research, as outlined by Myers and Well (2013), to examine the relationship between teachers' instructional appraisal literacy and students' interactions in diverse cultural settings. The study aimed to identify which aspects of teachers' appraisal literacy significantly impacted student interactions, focusing on observable behaviors rather than experimental conditions.

The respondents of the study were the students in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China. The sample size for the selection of the respondents was 195, which was taken from the total number of junior high school students in the selected public secondary schools. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the 150 respondents in this study. The study used specific inclusion criteria to select respondents: students with diverse learning styles, those who experienced various instructional appraisal practices, students with different language proficiencies, and those from diverse cultural backgrounds. Participants needed to voluntarily sign the Informed Consent Form (ICF) and have parental consent. The study focused on these criteria and did not account for students' socioeconomic status.

After validating the research questionnaire, the researcher undertook several key steps. First, they secured permission to conduct the study by obtaining an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, along with an ethics compliance certificate. These documents were included in the permission letters submitted to Kang Chiao International School Xi'an campus in China. Next, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to respondents following approval. The benefits of the survey were briefly explained, and respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires. Once collected, the data were organized by tallying scores per indicator. Finally, the researcher performed quantitative analysis using SPSS, applying both descriptive and inferential statistical methods to the gathered data.

The researcher adhered strictly to Rizal Memorial Colleges' Research Ethics principles throughout the study, ensuring social value by examining the impact of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers on student's interaction. Informed consent was obtained from respondents face-to-face, emphasizing their voluntary participation and the option to withdraw at any time. Measures were taken to ensure respondents' security and comfort during data collection, with stringent privacy standards in place to protect personal information. The study upheld the principle of justice by treating all participants equally and transparently sharing the study's methodology and findings. The researcher, supported by academic guidance and qualified for the study, utilized essential facilities and engaged the community by publishing the results to enhance understanding and support for the study's variables.

The collected data was thoroughly analyzed using various statistical techniques. The mean was used to characterize the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and student interaction in diverse cultural classrooms, addressing objectives 1 and 2 by measuring how scores clustered. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation assessed the significance of the relationship between instructional appraisal literacy and student interaction, providing insights for objective 3 by evaluating the strength of the linear relationship between paired data. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was applied to evaluate which domains of instructional appraisal literacy significantly influence student interaction in diverse cultural environments.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter highlighted the results and discussion of the study. The presentation starts from the descriptive analysis of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environments, followed by the discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation ends with the domains of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers predicts the students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China.

➤ *Level of Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers*

Table 1 shows the summary of the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers which are measured by four indicators namely: fairness and equity, students' involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Fairness and Equity (3.39) which was equivalent to moderate. Students' Involvement (3.34) which was equivalent to moderate. Further, Feedback and Communication (3.35) was moderate. Lastly, Technology in Assessment garnered a total mean score of (3.32) which was described as moderate. The overall mean score garnered in all the indicators was (3.35) described as moderate. This means that the summary of the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers which are measured by four

indicators namely: fairness and equity, students' involvement, feedback and communication, and technology

in assessment was moderate and was sometimes observed among teachers.

Table 1. Level of Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Fairness and Equity	3.39	Moderate
2	Students' Involvement	3.34	Moderate
3	Feedback and Communication	3.35	Moderate
4	Technology in Assessment	3.32	Moderate
	Overall Mean	3.35	Moderate

The overall instructional appraisal literacy of teachers, assessed across four indicators—fairness and equity, student involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment—is characterized as moderate. This indicates that while teachers generally demonstrate a reasonable level of competence in these areas, their practices are sometimes observed rather than consistently applied.

As viewed by Firoozi et al. (2019), instructional appraisal literacy is crucial for teachers at moderate levels as it allows them to assess the effectiveness of their teaching methods. This, in turn, enables them to make targeted improvements to enhance overall teaching effectiveness. Teachers with instructional appraisal literacy are better equipped to make informed decisions about instructional strategies, interventions, and adjustments to meet the diverse needs of students. This is particularly valuable at moderate levels where instructional decisions have a significant impact on student learning.

➤ *Level of Students' Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment*

Table 2 shows the Summary on the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment which are measured by four indicators namely: Interactive Learning, Cooperative Learning, Social Development, and Interpersonal Competence. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: *Interactive Learning* (3.34) which was described as moderate. *Cooperative Learning* (3.33) which was described as moderate. *Social Development* (3.39) which was described as moderate. Lastly, *Interpersonal Competence* (3.28) which was described as moderate. The four indicators/domains on the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment generates an over-all mean rating of (3.34), described as sometimes observed. This means that the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment namely interactive learning, cooperative learning, social development, and interpersonal competence has gained moderate result among teachers.

Table 2. Level of Students' Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Interactive Learning	3.34	Moderate
2.	Cooperative Learning	3.33	Moderate
3.	Social Development	3.39	Moderate
3.	Interpersonal Competence	3.28	Moderate
	Overall Mean	3.34	Moderate

The overall assessment of students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom, covering interactive learning, cooperative learning, social development, and interpersonal competence, reveals a moderate level of engagement. The mean ratings suggest that while these interactions are sometimes observed and contribute positively to the classroom environment, there is room for further enhancement to ensure more consistent and impactful engagement across all domains.

As noted by Tawa (2019), teachers at moderate levels should actively seek to integrate cultural competence into their teaching practices. This involves incorporating diverse perspectives into the curriculum, using culturally relevant examples, and being aware of different learning styles prevalent in a diverse cultural setting. Also, Helzelein (2016) noted that educators should employ inclusive pedagogical approaches that consider the varied cultural experiences and learning styles of students. This may

involve using diverse teaching materials, implementing differentiated instruction, and creating a classroom environment that values and respects different cultural norms.

➤ *Significant Relationship between Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers and Students' Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment*

Table 3 flaunted the data on the significant relationship between instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was applied for the two (2) variables on their significant relationship. The results appeared a computed p-value of .000 which was lower than the .05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected since the value denotes of having a significant relationship.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers and Students’ Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment

Variables		r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Instructional Appraisal Literacy (x)	Students’ Interaction (y)	0.87	Strong Positive correlation	.000	Reject H ₀

Furthermore, the computed r-value of 0.87 denotes the correlation between the two variables with which the hypothesis on significant relationship was tested. Clearly, the findings inferred a strong significant relationship between the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students’ interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi’an City, Shaanxi Province, China. Consequently, it is anticipated that improving teachers’ instructional appraisal literacy will enhance students’ interactions in a diverse cultural classroom environment, thereby positively influencing the overall classroom learning atmosphere.

The findings indicate a significant relationship between the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students’ interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District, Xi’an City, Shaanxi Province, China. This suggests that a high level of instructional appraisal literacy—such as the ability to effectively evaluate and adapt teaching practices to meet diverse cultural needs—enhances students’ interactions within the classroom. As teachers demonstrate strong appraisal skills, they are better able to create inclusive and responsive learning environments, which fosters improved student engagement, participation, and overall academic performance.

As mentioned by Adediwura et al. (2020), appraisal literacy promotes a student-centered approach to teaching. Teachers at moderate levels can use assessment data to understand individual student strengths and challenges, allowing for personalized and differentiated instruction. Teachers need to ensure that their instructional practices align with educational standards and curricular expectations. Instructional appraisal literacy enables teachers at moderate levels to evaluate the alignment of their teaching methods with established standards.

➤ *Domains of Instructional Appraisal Literacy of Teachers Predicts the Students’ Interaction in Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment*

Table 4 exemplified the regression test among instructional appraisal literacy namely: fairness and equity, students’ involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment towards instructional effectiveness. The overall correlation had a computed r-value of 0.87 with a p-value of <.000 in the significant level denotes the high positive correlation (Cohen, 2002) between the two variables with which the hypothesis on significant relationship was tested.

The findings indicate a very strong significant relationship between the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students’ interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment. The analysis shows an F-value of 67.83 with a p-value of <.000, indicating a statistically significant model fit. Additionally, the R² value of .7569 suggests that 75.69 percent of the variance in students’ interaction within the diverse cultural classroom environment is explained by the predictors, with the remaining variance attributed to factors not accounted for by the four dimensions under study.

Regression coefficients display that all the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers influences the students’ interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment. Likewise, unstandardized coefficients exhibit that among the domains of instructional appraisal literacy, fairness and equity with a coefficient of ($\beta=0.397$) had the best significant influence on the students’ interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment by displaying p-values which are lesser than .05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4. Domains of Instructional Appraisal Literacy Significantly Influence Students’ Interaction in a Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment

Instructional Appraisal Literacy	Students’ Interaction in a Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standard Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Decision @= 0.05
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Constant	1.908	.209		4.668	.000	
Fairness and Equity	.397	.085	.981	4.565	.000	Reject H ₀
Student’s Involvement	.334	.079	.601	6.432	.000	Reject H ₀
Feedback and Communication	.383	.085	.102	1.086	.001	Reject H ₀
Technology in Assessment	.243	.073	.384	4.057	.000	Reject H ₀

Dependent Variable: **Students’ Interaction in a Diverse Cultural Classroom Environment**
 R= 0.87, R²=0.7569, F-ratio=68.844 p-value= .000

Based on the above result, instructional appraisal literacy domains namely: fairness and equity, student's involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment significantly influences students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment by registering a p-value of .000 which is less than .05 in the level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further, the result indicates that for every unit increase in the four domains instructional appraisal literacy predictors, the students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment will increase by 1.908 holding other factors constant.

The analysis demonstrates a strong relationship between instructional appraisal literacy domains namely: fairness and equity, student's involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment and on the students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment, supported by a significant p-value indicating rejection of the null hypothesis. Each unit increase in these dimensions is predicted to result in an increase in students' interaction, holding other factors constant. The substantial R2 value of the variance in students' interaction can be explained by this instructional appraisal literacy of teachers. This underscores the influential role of effective instructional appraisal literacy in fostering stronger students' interaction and improving overall classroom dynamics.

On the study of Taylor (2021), result showed that instructional appraisal literacy plays a crucial role in enabling tailored instruction, as it provides teachers with the knowledge and skills necessary to adapt their teaching approaches to meet the individual learning needs of students. According to Shah Ahmadi and Ketabi (2019), appraisal-literate teachers can analyze assessment results to identify specific learning strengths and weaknesses of each student. This allows them to understand what concepts or skills students have mastered and where they might be struggling.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of fairness and equity: Teachers generally show strong awareness of fairness and equity in assessments, effectively addressing bias and identifying performance disparities. However, improvements are needed in providing accommodations, using clear language, and minimizing socioeconomic biases.

On the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of student's involvement: Teachers generally excel in encouraging student input on assessment methods and guiding students in analyzing their own results. However, there is a need for greater emphasis on promoting student ownership of the assessment process, facilitating discussions about the purpose of assessments, and involving students in setting assessment goals.

On the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of feedbacks and communications: Teachers generally perform well in using feedback for parent-teacher conferences and communicating assessment results clearly to parents and guardians. However, there is a need to improve in offering specific feedback that highlights student strengths, encouraging students to ask questions about their feedback, and consistently communicating assessment results.

On the level of instructional appraisal literacy of teachers in terms of technology in Assessment: Teachers generally excel in using adaptive learning technology and video conferencing tools for assessments. However, there is room for improvement in employing data visualization tools, integrating interactive simulations, and adapting assessment strategies for hybrid learning environments.

On the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of interactive learning: In a diverse cultural classroom, interactive learning is highly valued for promoting inclusivity and mutual respect. While students generally feel comfortable participating in discussions with peers from different backgrounds, and interactive learning enhances their understanding of various perspectives, engagement during activities and the overall quality of learning are observed to be moderate.

On the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of cooperative learning: In a diverse classroom setting, cooperative learning experiences are highly effective in fostering appreciation and respect for cultural diversity and enhancing students' ability to work with peers from different backgrounds.

On the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of social development: social development significantly contributes to a positive learning environment and fosters inclusivity and mutual understanding among students. While social interactions generally build a sense of community, and cultural diversity enhances the quality of these interactions, there is room for improvement in how actively students engage and promote understanding and respect.

On the level of students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in terms of interpersonal competence: students demonstrate high levels of respectful and empathetic communication, reflecting strong interpersonal skills. However, while the variety of cultural perspectives enhances the quality of interactions, and interpersonal competence contributes to a positive learning environment, there is variability in how effectively students communicate and collaborate.

Clearly, the findings inferred a strong significant relationship between the instructional appraisal literacy of teachers and students' interaction in diverse cultural classroom environment in Qujiang New District in Xi'an City, Shaanxi Province, China.

Based on the regression analysis, instructional appraisal literacy domains namely: fairness and equity, student's involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment significantly influences students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment by registering a p-value less than the level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further, the result indicates that for every unit increase in the four domains instructional appraisal literacy predictors, the students' interaction in a diverse cultural classroom environment will increase by holding other factors constant.

Based upon the outcomes of the findings, the following recommendations are suggested for consideration:

The Department of Education should invest in comprehensive training programs focused on fairness and equity in assessments, effective feedback practices, and the integration of technology. Additionally, policies should be developed to promote inclusive assessment practices and support the use of adaptive learning tools. Emphasizing the need for cultural competence in teaching and assessment can further strengthen the educational environment.

School heads should prioritize professional development opportunities for teachers, emphasizing the importance of fairness, equity, and clear communication in assessments. Implementing strategies to involve students more actively in the assessment process and leveraging technology effectively should be a key focus. Regularly reviewing and supporting the use of best practices in these areas can foster a more inclusive and effective learning environment. Facilitating collaborative sessions among teachers to share successful strategies for diverse classrooms can also be beneficial.

Teachers should continue to refine their practices in providing equitable assessments and clear feedback. Enhancing student involvement in the assessment process and utilizing technology to support diverse learning needs are crucial areas for development. Teachers should also strive to offer specific, actionable feedback and create opportunities for students to engage in goal-setting and reflection. Building a classroom culture that values diverse perspectives and cooperative learning can further improve student interactions and overall classroom dynamics.

Future research should explore the impact of specific instructional appraisal literacy practices on student outcomes in diverse cultural settings. Investigating how different aspects of fairness, feedback, and technology integration influence student engagement and academic performance could provide valuable insights. Additionally, examining the effectiveness of various professional development programs in improving instructional appraisal literacy and fostering inclusive learning environments would contribute to the ongoing improvement of educational practices.

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